

AUTOMATIC RAILWAY TRACK CRACK DETECTION SYSTEM USING GSM AND GPS

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Abstract: - Regular inspections of railway tracks are necessary for the purpose of finding physical problems or design non-compliances, which is crucial for safety reasons. Severe repercussions, including train derailments, might result from track flaws and non-compliances that are not recognised within a specific time span. With hundreds of thousands of miles of rail line, human inspectors are required to conduct inspections twice weekly to ensure safety requirements are met. However, there are a number of problems with this kind of manual inspection that might lead to a sloppy examination of the track, which could lead to accidents down the road. Because of the potential for such catastrophic mistakes and mishaps, an automated system was developed. This idea has the potential to automate the railway track inspection process, which in turn may reduce the likelihood of accidents caused by track defects.

Here we have implemented a train track fail detection robo along with the ultrasonic obstacle detection located on the track. The robo moves from the beginning point of the track travels until failure detection simultaneously calculates the distance from the starting point subsequently sense the failure information along with the distance of failure through sms.

KEYWORDS- Microcontroller; GPS Module; Railway Track

INTRODUCTION

It is a terrible shame that our country's railway rails are so vulnerable, as the railway is one of the most important forms of transportation in our nation. In light of this, it's no surprise that this antiquated system of

railway lines is responsible for a great deal of the annual loss of life. Incidents like this force us to consider the aforementioned problem and act to save lives. A safer, more contemporary train network is what we want to achieve with our suggested system. In addition to this, our nation does not have any technology or system that can prevent trains travelling in opposing directions on the same track from colliding. We are really interested in and deliberate about this topic. The distant location makes it exceedingly difficult, if not impossible, to swiftly remove any debris that a natural calamity may deposit on the rails. We reasoned that the control room might take precautions to prevent accidents if our system could identify such obstacles and relay that information. Figure 1 shows the track crack. There has been tremendous expansion in India's rail network recently. Even though it's a popular means of transportation, our infrastructure isn't up to date with what's required to meet international safety requirements. According to an online poll, derailments account for almost 60% of railway accidents; however, new data indicates that fractures in the tracks are responsible for roughly 90% of these incidents. Therefore, it poses a threat to human life. This must be given the highest priority. No one pays attention to them, and the tracks aren't kept in good repair. The job used to be done by hand in the old system, but this new one uses a robot that runs autonomously on the tracks. The system has an LED and LDR sensor assembly, but the biggest drawback is that the two components need to be in the exact opposite corners of the room for the track to be detected. To get over this drawback, sensors are used here to correctly identify the break. The current method is laborious, tedious, and sluggish. The system's GSM and GPS module will send the closest train station an SMS with the user's current position or coordinates.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

display a few number of characters at most. Adding a refresh controller to the LCD, which

takes the refresh duty out of the CPU's hands. In contrast, the data can only be shown until the CPU refreshes the LED. Character and graphic programming made easy. Standard IC circuits are unable to activate these components since they are "specialised" for use with microcontrollers. Various messages may be shown on a small LCD using them. Most often utilised in practice is a model detailed here because to its inexpensive price and wide possibilities.

Power Supply:

The Power Supply is a Primary requirement for the project work. The required DC power supply for the base unit as well as for the recharging unit is derived from the mains line. For this purpose center tapped secondary of 12V-012V transformer is used. From this transformer we getting 5V power supply. In this +5V output is a regulated output and it is designed using 7805 positive voltage regulator. This is a 3 Pin voltage regulator, can deliver current up to 800 milliamps.

LCD STANDS FOR LIQUID CRYSTAL DISPLAY:

For many reasons, LCD is quickly becoming the preferred technology over LEDs, particularly seven-segment LEDs and other multi-segment LEDs: The fall in LCD prices. Being able to show numbers, letters, and images. In comparison, LEDs can only

Led

One kind of semiconductor that may be used as a light source is the light-emitting diode (LED). Photons are released when electrons in a semiconductor recombine with electron holes. The energy needed for electrons to bridge the semiconductor's band gap determines the colour of the light, which is proportional to the photons' energy.[5] Either a coating of light-emitting phosphor applied to the semiconductor device or several semiconductors working together produce white light.[6]

Early light-emitting diodes (LEDs) produced weak infrared (IR) light when they first appeared as usable electrical components in 1962.[7] Countless consumer devices make use of infrared LEDs in their remote control circuitry. Early light-emitting diodes (LEDs) had a weak output.

and only available in red. There are high-output modern LEDs available in visible, UV, and infrared wavelengths. Indicator lights, which employed early LEDs to replace tiny incandescent bulbs, and seven-segment screens were commonplace. Modern technology has enabled the creation of white light LEDs with a high output, making them ideal for use as indoor and outdoor lighting. Because of their rapid switching rates, LEDs have found usage in cutting-edge communications technology and have spawned new kinds of displays and sensors.

GPS: Global Positioning System tracking is a method of working out exactly where something is. A GPS tracking system, for example, may be placed in a vehicle, on a cell phone, or on special GPS devices, which can either be a fixed or portable unit. GPS works by providing information on exact location. It can also track the movement of a vehicle or person. So, for example, a GPS tracking system can be used by a company to monitor the route and progress of a delivery truck, and by parents to check on the location of their child, or even to monitor highvalued assets in transit. A GPS tracking system can work in various ways. From a commercial perspective, GPS devices are generally used to record the position of vehicles as they make their journeys. Some systems will store the data within the GPS tracking system itself (known as passive tracking) and some send the information to a centralized database or system via a modem within the GPS system

unit on a regular basis (known as active tracking) or 2-Way GPS.

that are compatible with TTL may utilise them. The MAX232 is a two-in-one device that can transform signals from RX to TX to

GSM Module:

This GSM module can accept any GSM network operator SIM card and act just like a mobile phone with its own unique phone number. Application like SMS control, data transfer, remote control and logging can be developed easily. An embedded system is a special-purpose system in which the computer is completely encapsulated by or dedicated to the device or system it Controls. Unlike a general-purpose computer, such as a personal computer, an embedded system performs one or a few pre-defined tasks, usually with very specific.

CTS to RTS. By using on-chip charge pumps and external capacitors, the drivers are able to provide TIA-232 voltage level outputs (about ± 7.5 volts) from a central 5-volt source. This allows for the incorporation of TIA-232 into devices that would not normally need the use of additional voltages.

The TIA-232 inputs, which may reach ± 25 volts, are reduced to the typical 5 volt TTL levels by the receivers. These receivers often exhibit a 1.3 volt threshold and a 0.5 volt hysteresis.

A pair of earlier chips, the MC1488 and MC1489, which translated RS-232 in a similar fashion, were succeeded by the MAX232. Twelve and twelve volts of power were needed for the MC1488 quad transmitter chip[1], but the MC1489 quad reception chip only needed five volts.[2] in The primary drawbacks of this previous system were its

MAX232

Maxim Integrated Products introduced the MAX232 integrated circuit in 1987. It takes signals from a TIA-232 (RS-232) serial port and changes them so that digital logic circuits

inability to handle digital logic above 5 voltsits two chips instead of one, and its power requirement of +/-12 volts.

AT89C52

The AT89C52 is a low-power, high-performance CMOS 8-bit microcomputer with 8K bytes of Flash programmable and erasable read only memory (PEROM). The device is manufactured using Atmel's high-density nonvolatile memory technology and is compatible with the industry-standard 80C51 and 80C52 instruction set and pinout. The on-chip Flash allows the program memory to be reprogrammed in-system or by a conventional nonvolatile memory programmer. By combining a versatile 8-bit CPU with Flash on a monolithic chip, the Atmel AT89C52 is a powerful microcomputer which provides a highly-flexible and cost-effective solution to many embedded control applications.

The AT89C52 provides the following standard features: 8K bytes of Flash, 256 bytes of RAM,

32I/O lines, three 16-bit timer/counters, a six-vector two-level interrupt architecture, a full-duplex serial port, on-chip oscillator, and clock circuitry. In addition, the AT89C52 is designed with static logic for operation down to zero frequency and supports two software selectable power saving modes. The Idle Mode stops the CPU while allowing the RAM, timer/counters, serial port, and interrupt system to continue functioning. The Power-down mode saves the RAM contents but freezes the oscillator, disabling all other chip functions until the next hardware reset.

OSCILLATOR 110592

It is possible to produce crystal oscillators that can oscillate across a broad frequency range, from a few kilohertz all the way up to several hundred megahertz. There are a lot of uses for crystal oscillator frequencies that are closely connected to other required frequencies, thus electronics wholesalers produce and carry hundreds of standard crystal frequencies. Deriving a large variety of frequencies from one reference frequency is made practicable using frequency multipliers, frequency divisions, and phase locked loop circuits. According to the UART column, the maximum common baud rate is less than 1,000,000, supposing that a clock pre-divider of 16 is converted to an exact integer baud rate.

IR SENSOR

IR LED emits infrared radiation. This radiation illuminates the surface in front of LED. Surface reflects the infrared light. Depending on reflectivity of the surface, amount of light reflected varies. This reflected light is made incident on reverse biased IR sensor. When photons are incident on reverse biased junction of this diode, electron-hole pairs are generated, which results in reverse leakage current. Amount of electron-hole pairs generated depends on intensity of incident IR radiation. More intense radiation results in more reverse leakage current. This current can be passed through a resistor so as to get proportional voltage. Thus as intensity of incident rays varies, voltage across resistor will vary accordingly.

Circuit is divided into two sections. IR TX and IR RX are to be soldered on small general purpose Grid PCB. From this module, take out 3 wires of sufficiently long length (say 1 ft). Then, as shown

above, connect them to VCC, preset and to ground on main board. By adjusting preset, you can adjust sensitivity of the sensor. VCC should be connected to 5V supply.

enable input is high, the associated driver gets enabled. As a result, the outputs become active and work in phase with their inputs. Similarly, when the enable input is low, that driver is disabled, and their outputs are off and in the high-impedance state.

L293D MOTOR DRIVER

L293D is a dual H-bridge motor driver integrated circuit (IC). Motor drivers act as current amplifiers since they take a low-current control signal and provide a higher-current signal. This higher current signal is used to drive the motors. DC Motor In its common mode of operation, two DC motors can be driven simultaneously, both in forward and reverse direction. The motor operations of two motors can be controlled by input logic at pins 2 & 7 and 10 & 15. Input logic 00 or 11 will stop the corresponding motor. Logic 01 and 10 will rotate it in clockwise and anticlockwise directions, respectively. Enable pins 1 and 9 (corresponding to the two motors) must be high for motors to start operating. When an

ULTRASONIC SENSOR

An **ultrasonic sensor** is an instrument that measures the distance to an object using **ultrasonic** sound waves. An **ultrasonic sensor** uses a **transducer** to send and receive **ultrasonic** pulses that relay back information about an object's proximity. Ultrasonic sensors work by sending out a sound wave at a frequency above the range of human hearing. The transducer of the sensor acts as a microphone to receive and send the ultrasonic sound. Our ultrasonic sensors, like many others, use a single transducer to send a pulse and to receive the echo. The sensor determines the distance to a target by measuring time lapses between the sending and receiving of the ultrasonic pulse.

The working principle of this module is simple. It sends an ultrasonic pulse out at 40kHz which travels through the air and if there is an obstacle or object, it will bounce back to the sensor. By calculating the travel time and the speed of sound, the distance can be calculated.

Ultrasonic sensors are a great solution for the detection of clear objects. For liquid level measurement, applications that use infrared sensors, for instance, struggle with this particular use case because of target

translucence.

For presence detection, ultrasonic sensors detect objects regardless of the color, surface, or material (unless the material is very soft like wool, as it would absorb sound.)

To detect transparent and other items where optical technologies may fail, ultrasonic sensors are a reliable choice.

ROBO MOTOR

In any electric motor, operation is based on simple electromagnetism. A current-carrying conductor generates a magnetic field; when this is then placed in an external magnetic field, it will experience a force proportional to the current in the conductor, and to the strength of the external magnetic field. As you are well aware of from playing with magnets as a kid, opposite (North and South) polarities attract, while like polarities (North and North, South and South) repel. The internal configuration of a DC motor is designed to harness the magnetic interaction between a current-carrying conductor and an external magnetic field to generate rotational motion. Let's start by

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being electrically connected to the commutator. The above diagram shows a common motor layout with the rotor inside the stator (field) magnets.

looking at a simple 2-pole DC electric motor

(here red represents a magnet or winding with a “North” polarization, while green represents a magnet or winding with a “South” polarization).

Every DC motor has six basic parts — axle, rotor (a.k.a., armature), stator, commutator, field magnet(s), and brushes. In most common DC motors (and all that Beamers will see), the external magnetic field is produced by high-strength permanent magnets. The stator is the stationary part of the motor i.e., this includes the motor casing, as well as two or more permanent magnet pole pieces. The rotor (together with the axle and attached commutator) rotates with respect to the stator. The rotor consists of windings (generally on a core), the windings

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

CONCLUSION

Utilising an autonomous vehicle for the purpose of inspecting and detecting cracks in railway tracks would greatly enhance track maintenance and significantly reduce the likelihood of train accidents. This vehicle makes short work of areas where human inspection is impractical, such as deep coal mines, mountainous areas, and densely forested regions. When used for railway track inspection and crack detection, this vehicle's sensors may automatically send an SMS to a pre-defined phone number anytime they detect any deformation or fracture. This will greatly aid in the accurate monitoring and maintenance of railway tracks, which in turn will keep the rails in excellent condition and greatly reduce the likelihood of train accidents. An autonomous vehicle created specifically for use on railway tracks can spot irregularities like cracks, which, if fixed promptly, may significantly cut down on train accidents. An extra perk that contributes to power conservation is the installation of solar panels. The suggested solution does more than just fix these issues; it also makes rail fracture

detection more accurate. As far as our country's railroads are concerned, this is the most cost-effective strategy to reduce accident statistics. This might prevent the loss of economic capital and the loss of life among passengers. Additionally, it reduces the cost and effort needed to detect cracks.

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